

ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF DADIH ORIGINATED *LACTOBACILLUS CASEI* SUBSP. *CASEI* R-68 AGAINST FOOD BORNE PATHOGENS

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Abstract - The expectations of probiotic bacteria have become the most demanding for any bacterial group. Probiotics have become a very important element to everyday health food products. The purposes of the study were to compare the antibacterial activity of *Lactobacillus casei* subsp. *casei* R-68 (LCR68) and *Lactobacillus casei* Strain Shirota (LCS) against food borne pathogens (*Staphylococcus aureus* FNCC-15, *Listeria monocytogenes* FNCC-0156, *Escherichia coli* FNCC-19 and *Salmonella typhi*), to evaluate the antibacterial compound responsible for inhibiting the food borne pathogens and to assay the resistance of both *L. casei* strains to various types of antibiotic. Assay for antibacterial activity was tested using the well diffusion method and test for resistance to antibiotic was performed by employing disc diffusion method. The data obtained were tabulated and analyzed descriptively. The results showed that LCR68 and LCS inhibited the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* FNCC-15, *Listeria monocytogenes* FNCC-0156 and *Escherichia coli* FNCC-19 but did not inhibit the growth of *Salmonella typhi*. In general, antibacterial activity of LCR68 was slightly lower than that of LCS. Both *L. casei* strains strongly inhibited the growth of *Escherichia coli* FNCC-19 than *Listeria monocytogenes* FNCC-0156 and *Staphylococcus aureus* FNCC-15, respectively. Antibacterial activity of LCR68 and LCS was resistant to heat treatment (60-95°C), amylase and various proteolytic enzymes, but was very sensitive to pH treatments (pH 4-9). Both LCR68 and LCS were also resistant to various types of antibiotic. It is concluded that antibacterial compound of LCR68 and LCS was organic acid mainly lactic and acetic acids.

INTRODUCTION

Allen *et al.*, (2011) stated that the main requirement the strain can be used as a probiotic agent is having resistance against acid and bile acids as well as producing antibacterial substance so that it can lessen the growth of pathogenic bacteria and being resistant against antibiotic. One of the probiotic lactic acid bacteria (LAB) originated from genus of *Lactobacillus* that can produce antibiotic compound is *Lactobacillus casei*. The finding of a study carried out by Sunaryanto *et al.*, (2014) indicated that *Lactobacillus casei* significantly reduced the growth of pathogenic bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. These two types of bacteria are

pathogenic bacteria that often cause human beings to suffer from diseases such as diarrhea especially children. Besides, they can also cause infections in other parts of bodies outside intestines. According to Jawetz and Adelberg (2005) *Staphylococcus aureus* had the highest percentage of resistance against antibiotic that was 77 % followed by *Escherichia coli* which was 12 %.

Some of LAB strains have been isolated from several sources, among others the so called dadih which is a fermented milk product in a bamboo tube. Hosono *et al.*, (1989) stated that dadih has four kinds of LAB genus being potential to be used as probiotic namely: *Lactobacillus*, *Streptococcus*, *Leuconostoc* and *Lactococcus*. One of the potential

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Lactobacillus strains contained in dadih was *Lactobacillus casei* subsp. *casei* R-68.

Lactobacillus casei subsp. *casei* R-68 (LSR68) and others LAB isolated from dadih had the ability to cholesterol level in rats by taurocholic acid deconjugation (Pato and Hosono, 2004), had the potential as anti-cancer because LAB have the antimutagenic properties by binding mutagenic compounds such as N-Nitrosodiethylamine (NDEA) and N-nitrosodimethylamine (NDMA), N-nitrosopyrrolidine (NPYR) and N-nitrosopiperidine or NPIP (Hosono *et al.*, 1990) and Trp-P1 (Surono *et al.*, 2009) and the mutagenic compound that arise in tauco due to heating at a high temperature (Pato, 2003) as well as had resistance ability to gastric and bile acids (Pato, 2003). Other requirements need to be met in order to be used as a probiotic is the ability to produce antimicrobial/antibacterial compounds (Prado *et al.*, 2008). Antibacterial compound is a chemical or biological compound that can inhibit the growth and activity of pathogenic bacteria. Many bacterial pathogens contaminate food and cause illnesses such as *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Salmonella typhi*. Some researchers have reported the ability of LAB to inhibit the growth of food borne pathogens. Guessas *et al.*, (2005) reported the ability of LAB *Lactococcus lactis* subsp. *lactis* biovar *diacetylactis* Lc8 to inhibit the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*. Some of the genus *Lactococcus* and *Streptococcus* sp isolated from raib, a type of traditional fermented milk products in Algeria, inhibited the growth of some microbial pathogens such as *Listeria innocua*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus epidermididis* (Mezaini *et al.*, 2009). Jamuna and Jeevaratnam (2004) reported an antibacterial compound in the form of bacteriocin produced by *Pediococcus* sp inhibited the growth of *Listeria monocytogenes*. LAB was also able to inhibit the growth of *E. coli* (Al-Allaf *et al.*, 2009; Tatsadjieu *et al.*, 2009; Saranya and Hemashenpagam, 2011) and *Salmonella* sp (Al-Allaf *et al.*, 2009; Tatsadjieu *et al.*, 2009).

Antibiotic susceptibility of intestinal microorganisms is important because administration of antimicrobial substances can cause the suppression of certain beneficial bacterial groups, including *Lactobacillus* which promote natural resistance of the host gut infection. As a result, the altered microbial balance may result in intestinal disorders (Kobayashi *et al.*, 1973; Mitsuoka, 1989). Antibiotic therapy is used to combat bacterial

infections and this can in turn induce digestive disorders due to alteration of normal gut flora. Therapy with any antibiotic, particularly long term and especially oral administration is liable to alter the balance of antibiotic-resistant to sensitive organisms in the intestine (Drasar and Hill, 1974).

The purposes of this study were to compare the antibacterial activity and antibiotic susceptibility of *Lactobacillus casei* subsp. *casei* R-68 and commercial *Lactobacillus casei* strain Shirota, and to determine their antibacterial compound.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Lactic acid bacteria and pathogenic bacteria

In this research the dadih isolate used was *Lactobacillus casei* subsp. *casei* R-68 (LCR68). The commercial *Lactobacillus casei* strain Shirota (LCS) was used as the comparison probiotic LAB. Pathogenic bacteria used were *Staphylococcus aureus* FNCC-15 and *Listeria monocytogenes* FNCC-0156 which are Gram-positive bacteria, and *Escherichia coli* FNCC-19 and *Salmonella typhi* that belong to Gram-negative bacteria.

Activation of *Lactobacillus casei* strains and pathogenic bacteria cultures

Active culture made by taking 100 μ L of work culture of LCR68 and LCS was put into each tube containing 5 mL of MRS broth and incubated at 37°C for 18 h. The tested bacteria culture (pathogenic bacteria) were activated by inoculating 100 μ L of tested bacterial into 5 mL of Nutrient Broth and incubated at 37°C for 18 h. LAB and pathogenic bacteria were subcultured three times before using for any test.

Antibacterial activity of *Lactobacillus casei* strains

The antibacterial activity of *L. casei* strains was assessed using a well diffusion method according to procedure described by NCCLS (2000). The sterile Nutrient Agar (NA) medium was put into a petridish and left until it was solid at the room temperature. The test bacteria of 100 μ L was inoculated and then flattened with a hockey stick until it was dry. Then a well was built by using a sterile blue tip and was coated with sterile agar. As much as 100 μ L of a free-cell supernatants were poured into a well then incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The diameter of a clear zone formed was measured.

The Antibacterial sensibility of against, heat, enzymes and pH

The determination of antibacterial sensibility of LCR68 and LCS against acid, heat, and proteolytic enzyme was performed using a method described by Mezaini *et al.*, (2009). The cell-free supernatants were obtained by centrifugation at 8000 rpm for 20 min and filtered across cellulose acetate filter (0.2 µM) to remove residual cells. The cell-free supernatants were heated at the temperature between 60-95°C for 3 min (sensitivity test against heat) and pH was set up between 4-8 (sensitivity test against pH). To find out the kind of antibacterials (bacteriocin or not) the cell-free supernatants were added with each α-amylase enzyme (Sigma; 1 mg/mL in 100mM phosphate buffer solution, pH 6.9, α-chymotrypsin (Sigma; 1 mg/mL, 0.05M in Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0)-0.01M CaCl₂), Pronase E (Sigma; 1 mg/mL in 100mM Tris-HCl buffer, pH3), Proteinase K (Sigma; 1 mg/mL in 100mM Tris-HCl buffer, pH 7.5), or Trypsin (Sigma; mg/mL in 50mM Tris-HCl buffer, pH 8.0). Then the enzymes were inactivated by heating at 100°C for 3 min. The cell-free supernatants were then tested against various kinds of pathogenic bacteria. The cell-free supernatants added with buffer, heated cell-free supernatants at 100°C for 3 min, dissolving buffer and enzymes were used as the control. The clear zone diameters formed were measured.

Resistance of *Lactobacillus casei* strains against antibiotic

Assay for resistance of LCR68 and LCS against antibiotic was performed by using disc diffusion method according Bauer *et al.*, (1966). The antibiotic chosen were amoxicillin, cefadroxil, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin and tetracycline because the five kinds of antibiotics are frequently used by Indonesia people today (Anonim, 2015). Cultures of LCR68 and LCS were inoculated in MRS broth at 37 °C for 24 h. Then 100 µL of each bacterial suspension were taken and spread evenly on the surface of the MRS agar plate. The inoculated plate was allowed to dry before placing the diffusion discs containing antibiotics. The paper discs were placed on the surface of the agar plates. The amount of amoxicillin, cefadroxil, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin and tetracycline being put into paper disc were 50 µL containing 5 mg, 0.5 mg and 0.05 mg antibiotics, respectively and then incubated at 37°C for 24 h. Inhibition zone diameters were measured

inclusive of the diameter of the discs. Results were expressed as sensitive, S (= 21 mm); intermediate, I (16-20 mm) and resistant, R (= 15 mm), respectively according to that described by Vlková *et al.* (2006).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Antibacterial activity of cell-free supernatants of *Lactobacillus casei* strain

The cell-free supernatants were obtained by separating the cells and liquid medium using a centrifuge at 8000 rpm for 20 min. The separation was carried out to obtain metabolic compounds produced by LAB in the form of secondary metabolite so that the antibacterial agents could be identified. Savadogo *et al.*, (2004) stated that cell-free supernatants are obtained through a centrifugal process to separate the bacterial cells so that supernatant only contains the products of bacterial metabolism. According to Seo *et al.*, (2001), secondary metabolite is one of the bacterial cell metabolism products that functions as self-defence. The inhibition zone by LCR68 and LCS is shown in Fig 1.

Figure 1 shows that the cell-free supernatants of LCR68 and LCS had the ability to inhibit the growth of pathogenic bacteria, that is; *Staphylococcus aureus* FNCC-15, *Escherichia coli* FNCC-19 and *Listeria monocytogenes* FNCC-0156 marked with the formation of a clear zone around the well, but both *L. casei* strains were unable to inhibit the growth of *Salmonella typhi*. The diameter of clear zone of the cell-free supernatants is shown in Table 1.

The data in Tabel 1 shows that the cell-free supernatants of LCR68 and LCS had antibacterial activity against three types of food borne pathogens. The cell-free supernatants of LCS had slightly higher inhibition zone compared to the cell-free supernatants casei of LCR68 against the three types of pathogenic bacteria marked with the size of the clear zone formed around the well. This might be due to the cell-free supernatants of LCS had lower pH value compared to the cell-free supernatants of LCR68 (Table 2). The activity of the cell-free supernatants of LCR68 and LCS took place because of the formation of organic acid mainly lactic acid that made the acidic condition in the medium so that sensitive pathogenic bacteria could not grow well. Tabel 1 also shows that the cell-free supernatants of both *L. casei* strains had the highest antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* FNCC-

19 of 7.35 to 9.70 mm, *Listeria monocytogenes* FNCC-0156 of 7.05 to 9.50 mm and *Staphylococcus aureus* FNCC-15 of 6.05 to 7.88 mm. It happened because *Escherichia coli* FNCC-19 known as Gram-negative bacteria was more sensitive against acid condition. Ray (2003) stated that the Gram-negative bacteria are more sensitive against low pH value compared to the Gram-positive bacteria. Lade *et al.*, (2006) classified the size of the bacteria inhibition zone into three criteria, i.e. moderate inhibition between 6-9 mm, strong inhibition between 10-14 mm, and very strong inhibition between 15-18 mm. Based on those criteria it can be said that the antibacterial activity of the two types of *L. casei* against three types of pathogen *Staphylococcus aureus* FNCC-15, *Escherichia coli* FNCC-19 and *Listeria monocytogenes* FNCC-0156 are categorized into medium inhibition zone. Shokryazdan *et al.*, (2014) also reported that the three isolated *L. casei* strains from baby feses were able to inhibit the growth of 12 pathogenic bacteria including *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *Listeria monocytogenes*.

The data in Figure 1 and Table 1 indicate that LCR68 and LCS had no ability to inhibit the growth of *S. typhi* which belong to Gram-negative bacteria. This occurred because *S. typhi* had different cell membrane structures compared to general cell structure of bacteria. *S. typhi* membrane cells have two membrane layers, namely; outer membrane and inner membrane (Kita and Nikaido, 1973). As a result, the two membrane layers caused the antibacterial components of the two strains of *L. casei* to be unable to inhibit the growth of *S. typhi*. This finding is contradictory to the finding of a study conducted by Amin *et al.*, (2009) which discovered that *L. casei* isolated from fresh vegetable was able to inhibit the growth of various pathogenic bacteria including *S. typhi*. Mazaya *et al.*, (2016) also reported two *Lactobacillus* sp., i.e. *L. plantarum* and *L. paracasei* isolated from milk product were able to inhibit the growth of several kinds of pathogen including *S. typhi*.

The acidic condition occurred by the formation of organic acid mainly lactic acid during fermentation process is shown in Table 2.

A higher inhibition zone by both *L. casei* strains against Gram-negative bacteria occurred because of the antibacterial compounds, that was mainly lactic acid. This acid was able to damage the permeability of Gram-negative bacteria by breaking down the outer membrane of the Gram-

negative bacteria. Alakomi *et al.*, (2000) revealed that lactic acid is the molecule that dissolves in water so that it can go through into the periplasm of Gram-negative bacteria through porin protein at the outer membrane. The permeability protector of the outer membrane called lipopolisaccharide (LPS) located at the surface of the membrane was damaged by lactic acid. The damage of outer membrane cells might cause the other antibacterial compounds such as diacetyl, hydrogen peroxide and bacteriocin entering the cytoplasmic membrane and then damaged the intracellular activity that finally killed the cells. However, this mechanism does not apply to the Gram-negative bacteria *S. typhi* that has two layers of cytoplasmic membrane.

The Sensitivity of antimicroba of *Lactobacillus casei* strains against heat, enzyme and pH

This test was intended to find out whether the antibacterial compound of LCR68 and LCS was resistant or sensitive to various heat, enzymes and pH treatments, and the results are shown in Tables 3, 4 and 5. Based on the data in Table 3 it is known that various heat treatments on the cell-free supernatants of LCR68 and LCS did not omit the antibacterial activity. The results of heat treatment showed that the cell-free supernatants for both LCR68 and LCS still possessed the ability to inhibit pathogenic bacteria that were slightly different from the control (without heat treatment). The antibacterial activity tended to decrease as the temperature increased from 70 to 95°C. The heating could kill the LAB cells and damaged the metabolic components but did not omit all its metabolic components such as organic acid, bacteriocin, and diacetyl so that its ability to inhibit the pathogenic bacteria was still present but its antibacterial activity decreased.

Table 3 shows that antibacterial compound of LCR68 was more sensitive against the heat temperature compared to LCS marked with the small size of the clear zone being formed around the well. It happened because LCS had a smaller pH value compared to LCR68 (Table 2).

To determine the type of antibacterial agent produced by both LCR68 and LCS which is bacteriocin (secondary metabolic compound in the form of peptide) or the compound that contained amylose, the sensitivity test against various proteolytic enzymes and amylase was performed and the results are presented in Tables 4, 5 and 6.

Tabel 1. Antibacterial activity of cell-free supernatants of *L. casei* strains against food borne pathogens

Source of supernatant	Inhibition zone (mm)			
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> FNCC-15	<i>Escherichia coli</i> FNCC-19	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> FNCC-0156	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. <i>casei</i> R-68	6.05	7.35	7.05	0*
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota	7.88	9.70	9.50	0

*0 = No antibacterial activity

Fig. 1 Antibacterial activity of *Lactobacillus casei* strains against (a) *S. aureus* FNCC-15, (b) *E. coli* FNCC-19, (c) *L. monocytogenes* FNCC-0156 and (d) *S. typhi***Table 2.** pH value the cell-free supernatants of *Lactobacillus casei* strains

Source of supernatant	pH
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. <i>casei</i> R-68	4.25
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota	3.90

The data in Tables 4, 5 and 6 show that the antibacterial compound produced by both LCR68 and LCS strains was resistant against the treatment of various types of amylolytic and proteolytic enzymes which was marked with the presence of the inhibition zone against three types of pathogen. This means that the antimicrobial compound of both LCR68 and LCS strains was not in the form of peptide which is composing the bacteriocin, or not the compound containing amylose.

The inhibition mechanism against pathogenic bacteria by antibacterial compound of the cell-free supernatants was very likely caused by organic acid mainly lactic acid that created acidic condition at the growth medium. LCS had a smaller pH value compared to the pH of LCR68 so that the inhibition zone produced by LCS was bigger because the pathogenic bacteria could not survive in the acidic condition. The antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* FNCC-19 was bigger compared to *Staphylococcus aureus* FNCC-15. It happened because organic acid in the form of lactic acid was more able to damage the cell wall of *Escherichia coli* FNCC-19 known as the Gram-negative bacteria. Rahayu (2013) stated that lactic acid is an antibacterial compound with a wide inhibiting spectrum. To determine whether the antibacterial compound produced by both LCR68

Table 3. Sensitivity of antibacterial activity from *Lactobacillus casei* strains against various heat temperatures

Source of Supernatan	Temperature	Inhibition zone (mm)			
		<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> FNCC-15	<i>Escherichia coli</i> FNCC-19	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> FNCC-0156	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. casei R-68	Control (no heat treatment)	6.63	8.00	7.10	0*
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota		8.05	9.65	8.50	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. casei R-68	60°C	4.58	7.63	6.55	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota		7.85	9.58	8.30	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. casei R-68	70°C	3.88	7.53	6.90	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota		7.20	9.08	8.30	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. casei R-68	80°C	3.80	7.48	5.90	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota		7.13	8.85	7.90	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. casei R-68	90°C	3.78	7.15	4.95	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota		6.93	8.35	7.45	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. casei R-68	95°C	3.03	4.03	3.90	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota		6.80	7.25	6.70	0

*0 = No antibacterial activity

Table 4. Sensitivity of antibacterial activity from *Lactobacillus casei* strains against α amylase enzyme

Source of Supernatants	Inhibition zone (mm)			
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> FNCC-15	<i>Escherichia coli</i> FNCC-19	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> FNCC-0156	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>
		Heat treatment		
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. casei R-68	8.11	10.51	10.01	0*
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota	8.53	10.91	10.30	0
		No heat treatment		
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. casei R-68	8.11	11.53	10.05	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota	8.45	11.93	10.05	0

*0 = No antibacterial activity

Table 5. Sensitivity of antibacterial activity from *Lactobacillus casei* strains against proteinase K enzyme

Source of Supernatan	Inhibition zone (mm)			
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> FNCC-15	<i>Escherichia coli</i> FNCC-19	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> FNCC-0156	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>
		Heat treatment		
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. casei R-68	9.20	9.52	9.51	0*
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota	9.27	9.72	9.52	0
		No heat treatment		
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. casei R-68	8.83	9.32	9.17	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota	9.20	9.95	9.45	0

*0 = No antibacterial activity

and LCS was resistant to or sensitive against the change of the pH value, it was necessary to conduct a test and the results are shown in Table 7. Data in Table 7 indicate that LCR68 and LCS were

lost their antibacterial activity after the pH medium was set up by adding NaOH 1 N. The two types of LAB did not have the ability to inhibit the growth of pathogenic bacteria at pH 5, 6, 7, 8 dan 9,

Tabel 6. Sensitivity of antibacterial activity from *Lactobacillus casei* strains against trypsin enzyme

Source of Supernatan	Inhibition zone (mm)			
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> FNCC-15	<i>Escherichia coli</i> FNCC-19	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> FNCC-0156	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>
		Heat treatment		
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. <i>casei</i> R-68	9.35	10.03	9.53	0*
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota	9.82	10.07	9.87	0
No heat treatment				
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. <i>casei</i> R-68	8.72	10.97	9.73	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota	1,37	11.48	10.35	0

*0 = No antibacterial activity

Tabel 7. Sensitivity of antibacterial activity from *Lactobacillus casei* strains against various pH values

Source of Supernatan	Temperature	Inhibition zone (mm)			
		<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> FNCC-15	<i>Escherichia coli</i> FNCC-19	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> FNCC-0156	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. <i>casei</i> R-68	Control	5,55	7,38	7,05	0*
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota		6,43	8,78	8,40	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. <i>casei</i> R-68	5	--	--	--	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota		--	--	--	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. <i>casei</i> R-68	6	--	--	--	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota		--	--	--	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. <i>casei</i> R-68	7	--	--	--	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota		--	--	--	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. <i>casei</i> R-68	8	--	--	--	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota		--	--	--	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. <i>casei</i> R-68	9	--	--	--	0
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota		--	--	--	0

*0 = No antibacterial activity ; -- = Lost of antibacterial activity

which indicated that the antibacterial compound produced by LCR68 and LCS was organic acid. It means that the ability of LCR68 and LCS in inhibiting the growth of pathogenic bacteria was very likely caused by organic acid. *L. casei* is a facultative homofermentative lactic acid bacterium, producing 2 lactic acid molecules from every glucose molecule. It also produces small quantities of acetate, ethanol and diacetyl (Anonim, 2012). Lactic and acetic acids reduced the pH of the growth medium that created acid condition causing the pathogenic bacteria to be sensitive and unable to grow. Similar results were reported by Shokryazdan *et al.*, (2014) for *L. casei* Shirota, *L. casei* BF strain, *L. acidophilus*, *L. fermentum*, and Jin (1996) and Neal-McKinney *et al.*, (2012) for *Lactobacilli* and Keersmaecker *et al.*, (2006) for *L. rhamnosus* GG to inhibit various pathogens. Buckle *et al.*, (2007) also revealed that lactic acid produced by LAB could

reduce the pH value of its growing environment making the acidic condition that causes LAB to inhibit the growth of several types of microbes. The results of this study were contradictory to the finding of the research carried out by Amdekar *et al.* (2010) who discovered that the antibacterial compound of *L. casei* ATCC 334 against pathogenic bacteria *E. coli*, *P. fluorescens*, *S. enteritidis* and *K. pneumonia* was caused by the protein compound in the form of bacteriocin. Other possibility of antibacterial compound of *L. casei* and *Lactobacilli* belong to heterofermentative group was hydrogen peroxide and diacetyl (Saranya and Hemashenpagam, 2011).

The Resistance of *Lactobacillus casei* strains against various types and concentration of antibiotic

The types of antibiotic chosen were amoxicillin,

Table 8. Resistance of *Lactobacillus casei* strains against Various Types and Concentration of antibiotics

Type and concentration antibiotics	Inhibition zone (mm)	
	<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> subsp. <i>casei</i> R-68	<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> strain Shirota
Amoxicillin		
0.05 mg	0	0
0.5 mg	0	0
5.0 mg	0	0
Cefadroxil		
0.05 mg	0	0
0.5 mg	0	0
5.0 mg	0	0
Erythromycin		
0.05 mg	0	0
0.5 mg	0	0
5.0 mg	0	0
Ciprofloxacin		
0.05 mg	0	0
0.5 mg	0	0
5.0 mg	0	0
Tetracyclin		
0.05 mg	0	0
0.5 mg	0	0
5.0 mg	0	0

cefadroxil, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin and tetracycline because these five types of antibiotic are often consumed by the Indonesian people (Anonim, 2015). These types of antibiotic are used to kill microba particularly pathogenic bacteria that bring about diseases to human beings. They can kill the bacteria of positive and negative gram bacteria. The two types of *L. casei* belong to lactic acid bacteria and Gram-positive group. As probiotic candidate, LCR68 must be resistant to various kinds of antibiotic; so, it is expected that its amount in the gastrointestinal tract remains sufficient to perform its therapeutic function. The result of the resistance test against different doses and types of antibiotic are presented in Table 8. The data in Table 8 show that both LCR68 and LCS strains had the same resistance against various types and concentration of antibiotics which marked by the absence of the inhibition zone against the growth of LCR68 and LCS. Therefore, it is expected that LCR68 is able to perform its therapeutic function towards patients who are consuming one of the types of this antibiotic. The finding of this research is supported by some previous finding research. Saranya and Hemashenpagam (2011) who reported the

resistance of *L. casei* isolated from fermented milk product against seven types of antibiotic, namely; Rifampicin, Ketoconazole, Novobiocin, Fluconazole, Gentamycin, Amphotericin and Chloramphenicol. Liasi *et al.*, (2009) reported the resistance of *L. casei* against 11 types of antiobiotic but not sensitive against 7 kinds of antibiotic. Srinu *et al.*, (2013) stated the resistance of *L. casei* 297 against 7 types of antibiotic i.e, Ampicillin (10 mcg), Nalidixic acid (30µg), Ciprofloxacin (30µg), Gentamicin (10µg), Cefpodoxime (10µg), Co-Trimoxazole (25µg) and Tetracycline (10µg).

Klare *et al.*, (2007) also discovered three *Lactobacillus* strains that were resistant to Streptomycin, 17 *Lactobacillus* isolates were resistant to *Erythromycin*, *Clindamycin*. The finding of a clinical study proved that the consumption *L. casei* Shirota by elderly patients of Antibiotic-Associated Diarrhoea (AAD) and *C. difficile* Infection (CDI) could reduce the total bacteria and Bifidobacterium and could also increase the amount of *Lactobacilli* (Pirker *et al.*, 2012). The resistance to tetracycline is often found with *Lactobacilli* (Roberts, 2005; Korhonen *et al.*, 2008). Resistance to neomycin, kanamycin, streptomycin and gentamicin (aminoglycosides) was also found in *Lactobacilli* (Coppola *et al.*, 2005; Danielsen, 2002; Zhou *et al.*, 2005). Different results reported by Shokryazdan *et al.*, (2014) who discovered *L. casei* strains isolated from baby feces were not resistant to several tested antibiotics. Sato *et al.*, (2004) revealed that the resistance and sensitivity against antibiotic of LCS and most *Lactobacilli* do not involve genes encoding and are not descended genetically. The sensitivity against penicillin and ampicillin was caused by cell wall synthesis inhibitor (Danielsen and Wind, 2003; Coppola *et al.*, 2005); the resistance against vancomycin was caused by intrinsic factors (Tynkkynen *et al.*, 1998). *Lactobacilli* is generally sensitive against chloramphenicol, erythromycin and clindamycin because of protein synthesis inhibitors (Coppola *et al.*, 2005; Klare *et al.*, 2007), while the resistance to trimethoprim is caused by nucleic acid synthesis inhibitor which may be an intrinsic factor (Ammor *et al.*, 2007).

CONCLUSION

Lactobacillus casei subsp. *casei* R-68 had the ability to inhibit the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* FNCC-15, *Listeria monocytogenes* FNCC-0156 and *Escherichia coli* FNCC-19 with a slightly smaller antimicrobial

activity compared to the commercial *Lactobacillus casei* strain Shirota. However, the two *Lactobacillus casei* strains were not able to inhibit the growth of *Salmonella typhi*. The antibacterial compounds produced by *Lactobacillus casei* subsp. *casei* R-68 and *Lactobacillus casei* strain Shirota were resistant to the heat treatment at the temperature between 60°C and 95°C and also resistant to various proteolytic enzymes and amylase but very sensitive against pH treatment of pH 5-9. Therefore, it can be concluded the main components of antimicrobe of the two strains of LAB was organic acids especially lactic and acetate acids. In addition, both *L. casei* strains were resistant to five types of antibiotic namely amoxicillin, cefadroxil, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin and tetracyclin up to concentration of 5 mg.

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